

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: High Temperature Testing of Rock Wool Insulation

This application highlights addresses the measurement of rock wool insulation at elevated temperatures (up to 600°C) using the Transient Plane Source (TPS) method.

Insulation is a material type used to reduce heat transfer in a system and maintain desired temperature conditions. Insulation materials are employed across a wide range of temperature-dependent applications and the type of insulation used is highly subject to the system requirements. The governing factor used in quantifying insulative performance is thermal conductivity, sometimes expressed in its reciprocal form as a function of thickness called R-value (or thermal resistance). Insulations are traditionally tested using steady-state methods such as Heat Flow Meters/Guarded Hot Plates. These methods' common limitations are the long test times, restrictive sample sizes and fixed testing condition requirements. Herein, we highlight the measurement of a rock wool insulation as a function of temperature using a transient-based method.

Figure 1 – Rock Wool Insulation (left) and C-Therm TPS500 Sensor (right).

The FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) method is available on the Trident platform and is recommended for measuring above 300°C. In this work, the mica-based TPS sensor was placed between two pieces of rock wool and assembled in a thermal chamber for testing. A metal enclosure was used to help isolate the test setup during the measurement. The data presented is the average of multiple tests for each temperature point (n=5). Results are compared to publication values on similar rock wool materials.

Figure 2 – Thermal Conductivity Results Compared to Published Literature Values.

The thermal conductivity of rock wool is noted to increase as a function of temperature. Results obtained followed a similar trend compared to literature results collected on similar rock wool materials.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com